

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING NEW PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN ENSURING STUDENTS' FOREIGN LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the relevance of foreign language learning in the modern world and focuses on the teaching of English as the most widely studied foreign language today. It highlights the development of students' skills and competencies in language learning, as well as the teaching methods applied in this process..

In recent years, profound changes and fundamental transformations have taken place in all spheres of our country. Especially after gaining independence, young people's interest in learning foreign languages has significantly increased, and the state has created—and continues to create—favorable conditions for language learning. This, of course, is not without reason.

In today's world, where deep transformations are underway, paying close attention to foreign language learning among young people is a demand of the time for a country striving to take a *достой* place in the global community. Moreover, for a nation building its great future in cooperation with foreign partners, proficiency in foreign languages is of paramount importance.

It is encouraging that today a growing number of young people meet international standards. The number of students achieving internationally recognized language certifications is increasing day by day. In addition, it is gratifying that graduates of our educational institutions are gaining admission to more than seven of the world's top 1000 universities. Undoubtedly, mastering any subject is a complex process, and acquiring a foreign language as proficiently as one's native language largely depends on the teacher's professional competence.

Language has always been regarded as a means of communication; without it, neither individuals nor society can develop. According to the requirements of the modern era, the use of new pedagogical approaches in ensuring students' foreign language proficiency is both important and effective. Compared to traditional lessons, classes conducted using modern technologies result in higher learning outcomes. However, it should be emphasized that first and foremost, teachers themselves must have a deep understanding of pedagogical and modern educational technologies.

Currently, the most widely used interactive teaching methods include case studies, blitz surveys, modeling, creative tasks, and problem-based learning. According to research, interactive teaching strategies also encompass brainstorming, boomerang, gallery walk, zig-

zag, step-by-step methods, icebreakers, rotation, and the snowball technique. These methods play a significant role in language learning; however, information technologies also occupy an important place in increasing their effectiveness.

Thus, language learning requires the development of specific communicative competencies, and the role of information technologies in enhancing these competencies is invaluable. Information technologies enable learners to exchange ideas in various situations during interaction with others and to use language and speech norms correctly. At this stage, the main goal of foreign language teaching is to develop communicative ability, that is, to enable interpersonal communication in a foreign language.

At every level of education—general secondary and vocational education—foreign language learning sets specific goals and objectives within the educational process. One of the primary tasks is to consider students' personal interests. This means that the teacher must first be able to arouse learners' interest in language learning. In addition, to achieve planned outcomes and set goals, teachers should know which technologies to apply in the educational process.

It is evident that no educational technology, regardless of how advanced it is, can alone create the most effective conditions for identifying and developing students' skills. Therefore, it is essential to address the concept of pedagogical technology.

Pedagogical (educational) technology refers to a well-designed model of teaching and learning activities that includes a favorable environment for both students and teachers, as well as the planning, organization, and implementation of the instructional process. Pedagogical technology encompasses the realization of a fully controllable educational process. Modern technologies include problem-based learning, multi-stage instruction, cooperative learning systems, technological approaches to inventive problem-solving, research-based teaching methods, and project-based learning.

In foreign language teaching, the use of game-based technologies is particularly significant. These include role-playing, business and other educational games, cooperative learning (team and group work), and information and communication technologies.

In conclusion, when teachers choose appropriate methods for language instruction and organize foreign language communication effectively, and when students are taught using modern methodologies, difficulties in foreign language learning are gradually eliminated. This, in turn, increases learners' motivation to study languages and requires both teachers and students to be inquisitive, proactive, and continuously engaged in self-improvement.

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